

Understanding Dental Implants: Key Findings From a Questionnaire Study

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Abstract

Background: Dental implants have become a popular treatment option for replacing missing teeth. The purpose of this study was to evaluate the knowledge, awareness, and attitudes of the Pondicherry population regarding dental implants as a treatment option for replacing missing teeth.

Materials and methods: This study included 2,570 participants aged 18 and above who visited the outpatient department of a tertiary dental hospital in Pondicherry. The participants received a self-explanatory questionnaire containing fifteen questions, which was distributed using Google Forms software and sent via email.

Results: A total of 1,230 participants completed the questionnaire. Of these, 44.5% preferred dental implants for replacing missing teeth and acknowledged the crucial role of dentists in educating the public about implant therapy. Approximately 39.5% cited the relatively high cost of implants as a barrier to acceptance. Additionally, 57.3% of the participants viewed fixed replacements as advantageous, primarily for their aesthetics and improved functionality.

Conclusion: Our study findings indicate that patients possessed knowledge about dental implant therapy and expressed willingness to consider them for replacing their missing teeth in the future. However, the relatively high cost emerged as a significant barrier to accepting implants. Ultimately, this study underscores the critical role of dentists in educating the public about the effectiveness of dental implants in treating tooth loss.

Keywords: dental implant, general knowledge, awareness, attitude, web-based surveys, and questionnaire.

Introduction

Tooth loss can lead to challenges in mastication, occlusion, temporomandibular joint disorders, and an esthetically displeasing appearance, all of which can have adverse effects on the overall physical well-being and social satisfaction of an individual.^(1,2) Tooth loss can also have adverse effects on oral health, potentially leading to drifting of adjacent teeth, supra eruption of opposing teeth, increased risk of further tooth loss, and the development of temporomandibular disorders (TMDs). The World Health Organization (WHO) categorizes individuals without teeth as physically weakened, emphasizing the loss of a crucial body part.⁽³⁾ Taking all these factors into account, it is essential to address edentulism through appropriate treatment.⁽⁴⁾ Treatment of edentulism, including fixed or removable partial dentures, as well as implant-supported prostheses, have tradition-ally

been utilized for restoring missing teeth. However, dental implants have emerged as the preferred choice in recent times due to their ability to offer long-term benefits with fewer complications.^(5,6)

The perspectives and attitudes of the population toward dental implants remain largely unclear. Therefore, it is crucial to conduct a survey aimed at assessing knowledge about dental implant as a treatment option for replacing missing teeth, their acceptance levels through feedback analysis.⁽⁷⁾ Ho K et al showed that patients generally have positive experiences with dental implants. However, there appears to be a deficiency in patient education regarding dental implants and their associated procedures.⁽⁸⁾ A Al-Haj

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Husain et al uncovered a positive attitude and a satisfactory level of awareness and understanding regarding the utilization of dental implants in treating edentulism.⁽⁹⁾

Nowadays, web-based surveys are becoming increasingly prevalent, especially in fields like evaluation research, in contrast to traditional paper based surveys. They facilitate the collection of large volumes of data through self administered electronic questionnaires distributed over the internet. This method eliminates the need for interviews, paper materials, or postage fees, and streamlines data processing by integrating data entry directly.⁽⁷⁾ In previous studies, the Indian population was found to have a significant knowledge gap regarding dental implants, whereas higher levels of awareness have been reported in other studies.⁽¹⁰⁾ Hence, the aim of the present study was to assess the general knowledge about dental implants in patients reporting to a tertiary dental hospital in Pondicherry using online questionnaire (Google forms software).

Materials & Methods

The present study was conducted to assess the general knowledge regarding dental implants in a total of 2,570 participants through online questionnaire (prepared using Google forms software) composing of 15 questions and assessed using percentage. The questionnaire was sent to the participants through their individual email IDs. All participants were informed about the aim and objectives of the study. Out of 2,570 participants contacted, only 1,230 chose to take part in the study.

The inclusion criteria consisted of individuals aged 18 years or older, reporting the outpatient department of a tertiary dental hospital in Pondicherry. Participants who did not express interest in the study were excluded. This web survey included self-explanatory questions consistent with prior study conducted by Hosadurga et al.⁽¹⁰⁾

Questionnaire

1. Do you have any missing teeth?
 - a) Yes
 - b) No
2. What would you like to have your teeth replaced with?
 - a) Removable prosthesis/appliances
 - b) Fixed prosthesis/appliances
 - c) Implants
 - d) Not replaced at all
3. Do you know about dental implants as a treatment option to replace missing teeth?
 - a) Yes
 - b) No
4. From where have you heard about dental implants?
 - a) Dentist
 - b) Family & friends
 - c) Medical doctor
 - d) Media
5. Do you think replacement of missing teeth is important?
 - a) Very important
 - b) Somewhat important
 - c) Neither important nor unimportant
 - d) Not at all

6. Where do you think dental implant is placed?
 - a) In the bone
 - b) In the gums
7. How long do you think a dental implant lasts?
 - a) Lifetime
 - b) More than 10 years
 - c) Less than 5-10 years
 - d) Not sure
8. How much do you think a patient have to pay for an implant in India?
 - a) Rs 10,000
 - b) Rs 10,000 to Rs 20,000
 - c) Rs 20,000 to Rs 30,000
 - d) More than Rs 30,000
9. Who in your opinion should opt dental implants for replacing their missing teeth?
 - a) Single tooth loss
 - b) Multiple tooth loss
 - c) Complete tooth loss
 - d) All the above
10. Do you think implants are effective in replacing missing teeth?
 - a) Yes
 - b) No
11. If yes, what are they?
 - a) Fixed replacement is better
 - b) Better esthetics
 - c) Better function
 - d) No grinding of teeth
12. What are the barriers to dental implant as a treatment modality?
 - a) Did not see the need for surgery
 - b) High cost
 - c) Fear of surgery
 - d) Not clear about the treatment procedure
13. Have you come across anybody with a dental implant?
 - a) Yes
 - b) No
14. If yes, how satisfied is he/she with the implant(s)?
 - a) Very satisfied
 - b) Satisfied
 - c) Not so satisfied
 - d) Unsatisfied
15. Are you willing to consider dental implant as a treatment modality in future?
 - a) Yes
 - b) No

Results

Demographic data of the participants

Figure 1: Age of the study participants

Figure 2: Sex of the study participants
Questionnaire for assessing the general knowledge about dental implants in the study participants

Figure 3: Assessing the percentage of edentulism among study participants

Figure 4: Choice of preference for replacing missing teeth among study participants

Figure 5: Knowledge about dental implants for replacing missing teeth among study participants

Figure 6: Source of information about dental implants among study participants

Figure 7: Assessment of importance regarding replacement of missing

teeth among study participants

Figure 8: Knowledge about dental implant placement among study participants

Figure 9: Perspective of implant survival among study participants

Figure 10: Perspective of implant cost charges among study participants

Figure 11: Opinion on opting dental implants among study participants

Figure 12: Assessing the effectiveness of replacing missing teeth in the study participants

Figure 13: Benefits of dental implants among study participants

Figure 14: Barriers for dental implant therapy among study participants

Figure 15: Participant's knowledge on patients who had previously undergone dental implant therapy

Figure 16: Satisfaction levels of patients who had previously undergone dental implant therapy

Figure 17: Acceptance rate of dental implants among study participants

Discussion

In the present study, when asked if the study participants would replace their missing teeth, approximately 44.5% of participants preferred dental implants, followed by fixed prostheses at 24.4%. In a previous study done by Mously HA et al, majority of the study participants chose dental implants for replacing missing teeth.⁽¹⁸⁾ Furthermore, when asked if they would restore their missing teeth with dental implants, 74.2% of the participants were aware of dental implants as a treatment option. Although, contrast findings were observed in an earlier study done by Ravi Kumar C et al, where the most preferred treatment for replacing missing teeth was fixed partial dentures (FPD).⁽¹⁴⁾ Additionally, 60.7% of participants considered replacing missing teeth to be very important, whereas only 8.2% did not feel the need to address edentulism. In the present study, 66.9% of the participants believed that implants were placed directly in the bone.

In the present study, it was also evident that dentists (64.4%) were the primary source of information on dental

implants, followed by family and friends (15.5%), media (14.5%), and medical doctors (5.6%). Hosadurga et al, in his study has also acknowledged the significant role dentists play in disseminating knowledge about dental implants.⁽¹⁰⁾ On the contrary, Berge TI et al. in his study have found out that media plays as a main source of information to the public about dental implants.⁽¹⁵⁾

Regarding the longevity of implants in the oral cavity, approximately 24.6% of the study participants reported that implants would last a lifetime, 30.3% believed they would last more than ten years, 22.1% said they would last between five and ten years, and 23% were unsure about the survival chances of dental implants. In another study, it was found that approximately 70% of the participants were uncertain about the possibility of implant survival.⁽¹⁸⁾ Another important factor influencing the decision to opt for implant therapy is the cost. Specifically, 28.1% chose Rs.10,000; 30.6% chose Rs.10,000 to Rs.20,000; 21.5% chose Rs.20,000 to Rs.30,000; and 19.8% chose more than Rs.30,000.

Nearly 45% of the participants opted dental implants for treating single tooth loss, multiple tooth loss, and complete tooth loss. However, these findings were not consistent with a previous study conducted by HA Mously et al., where most participants believed that implants were primarily indicated for replacing multiple missing teeth, followed by single missing teeth. More than two-thirds (82.6%) of the participants, who knew about dental implant answered that they were effective in replacing missing teeth.⁽¹⁸⁾ This probably indicates that participants, once familiar with implant-based treatments, would choose these options to replace their missing teeth and would generally be satisfied with the results.⁽⁷⁾ Also in the present study, participants chose dental implants for the following advantages namely; fixed replacement as a better option (57.3%), better esthetics (11.8%), better function (25.5%) and to prevent grinding of the adjacent tooth structures (5.4%). However, contrary reports were seen in a previous study where most of the participants opted for missing tooth replacement due to esthetics followed by difficulty in mastication.⁽¹⁸⁾

In the present study, when asked about the barriers preventing them from preferring dental implant therapy, 39.5% of participants cited the high cost, 27.7% mentioned fear of surgery, 17.6% were unclear about the treatment procedure, and 15.1% did not see the need for surgery. Similar findings in earlier studies also identified high treatment costs as a major disadvantage of implant therapy. When asked regarding satisfaction levels with implant therapy in our study, majority of the population (62.7%) reported being satisfied, while only 3.9% were unsatisfied. At the end of the questionnaire, more than two-thirds of the participants (83.5%) expressed a willingness to consider dental implants as a future treatment option for replacing missing teeth. Consequently, in the present study, constraints such as limited sample size and lower response rate may have impacted the validity of our findings.

Conclusion

Nearly half of participants were found to have knowledge about dental implants for replacing missing teeth. This study uncovered the significant role of dentists in educating the public about dental implants as an effective replacement for missing teeth. Additionally, the study highlighted that the relatively high cost of implants and fear of surgery were the primary hindrance for participants considering implant therapy. Furthermore, the importance of addressing edentulism was widely acknowledged among the study participants. Also, these web-based surveys seem to be more advantageous in terms of data collection and storage for future use. Further studies should focus on conducting thorough assessments of participants within a large and diverse population, while also exploring innovative methods to consistently spread knowledge about dental implant therapy.

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